

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Du Plessis****FIRST NAME: Vincent****PROGRAM CODE: MBASD****COURSE CODE: ACA401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 365 on Windows 10)

ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Growing up in a country with 11 official languages, one becomes desensitised to the details and intricacies of proper writing and the correct use of the English language. When English is everyone's second (or even third or fourth) language, everyday mistakes in grammar and punctuation becomes commonplace and one tends to overlook such mistakes very easily. In reviewing the assigned study material these mistakes became apparent. In this regard, the section on pages 46-53 of the course-pack was found to be very useful. These mistakes were however not the only matter that became apparent during the review of the assigned study material. Differences in referencing and citing of sources and writing styles in the Chicago Management Style (CMS) Crib Sheet on pages 66-77 also stood out. In addition, hereto, I was delighted to note the required use of formatting styles in MS Word. In the sections below, I explore my personal writing experiences (academic and otherwise) in reference to the assigned study material.

2) LANGUAGE 101 VS TAAL 101¹

My tertiary education commenced at the University of Stellenbosch, South Africa, which is a bilingual university. Students, therefore, had a choice in which language they wish to write papers, tests and exams in, either Afrikaans or English. Thus, for me, the choice was not really between UK or US conventions, but rather an entirely different language. At the time I choose to continue my education in my mother tongue (Afrikaans),

¹ Taal is the Afrikaans word for "Language".

I later realised that it might be more sensible to change to English as Afrikaans might limit my ability to communicate effectively on the international stage. The switch was not easy. Despite the limitations of Afrikaans, surprisingly I found Afrikaans to be very evolved language when one considers the extent to which it had developed in almost all academic subjects. Many of the terms and jargon had legitimate translations and the challenge was now to learn these in English. Even though it was not easy to overcome these challenges I realised that it was worth the effort. Unfortunately, I could not complete the qualification at the University of Stellenbosch due to some financial difficulty it did provide me with a foundation on which I could later build my English writing skills.

A few years later, after entering the workforce, I commenced with part-time studies at the University of South Africa. Here, some study modules were also offered in Afrikaans, however, I decided to stick with my earlier choice to continue my studies in English. My work at the time also required much writing in the form of report writing based on environmental impact assessments and scientific specialist studies. I am confident in my abilities in communicating effectively in English, but as I worked through the assigned study material, I realised that there are many things that I either did not know or entirely forgotten. South Africans, as residents of a former British colony, are schooled in the use of UK conventions, however over time English in South Africa has evolved to have a “local flavour” with its own conventions and unique manner of using the language.

Despite this evolution, formal written English, such as in the case of academic writing, remains based on the UK conventions. Although I had been aware of some differences between UK and US conventions, I did not pay much attention to it, save for the occasional spelling of “authorise” and “authorize”. It was therefore very interesting to note the grammatical differences explained in the assigned study material with regards punctuation, spelling and language use (EUCLID 2015, 54-59). I realised some of the mistakes I have been making. As noted, before, English in South Africa has taken on a “local flavour” and in many cases, save for a few purists, even lecturers became more tolerant to the smaller mistakes or confusions. The assigned study material was very helpful in understanding some of these differences and I realised that I must pay more attention to the details. Writing has always been something I enjoyed doing, but over time I had taken on some bad habits which went uncensored.

3) REFERENCING AND PLAGIARISM

During my academic career, I have become accustomed to using the Harvard style of referencing as this is the accepted style by the academic community in South Africa. This style uses intext referencing by citing the surname of the author/s and the year in which the work was published. The conclusion was then followed by a bibliography of publications consulted during the writing of the paper. I used the referencing/sources function in MS Word to ensure that I have a complete library of works and it was applied very effectively to insert in-text referencing. I must admit that I have never worked with footnote referencing nor with the Turabian style of referencing (EUCLID 2015, 66). I am also not familiar with the use of Zotero and Grammarly and feel rather unsure about the application thereof. However, following some reading on the functions and capabilities

thereof, I am very much looking forward to exploring and better understand the benefits thereof and will employ it in the future.

Even though I am familiar with the practice of intext referencing, I have never employed footnote referencing such as required for the final essays (EUCLID 2015, 36). To be frank I am not sure about the practicality of this, as it appears that the references must be typed out in the correct format and cannot be automatically inserted such as in the case of bibliographical references at the end of a paper. This, I believe, creates much room for mistakes and must be a time-consuming process. However, as noted above, I am not familiar with the use of Zotero and I am hoping that it might be employed to simplify the process.

I find it rather disconcerting that a text explaining the use of footnotes and that the use thereof should not confuse the reader, really confused me. It is unclear to me why a footnote would run over to the next page, as my understanding is that the purpose of using footnotes would be to allow for quick referencing, yet if it is at the top of the next page it serves no purpose and looks out of place. I do however agree with the author that footnotes can be a “bewildering maze” and can easily confuse a reader (EUCLID 2015,73-74). In addition, as eluded to above, the use of it as a referencing method seems confusing especially if a large number of sources are used. In my opinion, unless the reader is specifically interested in the references it creates clutter and confusion and makes the content difficult to read.

Regarding plagiarism, I have always prided myself to refrain from this practice. Up to now my strategy to avoid plagiarism was to relate the subject of the paper to personal experience and formulate responses and arguments based thereupon. As the arguments evolved during the writing process the paper took on a structure. In cases where the arguments were weak or required explanation, references were sought in support thereof. The paper, therefore, ended up being an original text of thoughts and arguments with minimal quotes or weak paraphrasing. Of course, not all ideas, thoughts and arguments were original this “free-writing” process allowed me to formulate my own thoughts and referencing it to existing academic literature. I don’t believe that there is a recipe for writing, each person develops their own process. Even though writing has rules in terms of the use of language, structure, style and conventions, it is not a linear process (EUCLID 2015, 2).

In cases where I had little or no knowledge of the subject or could not relate the problem to personal experience, I did some research on the subject until I found an angle that I could relate to. I would then build on this by following the abovementioned process. I find it difficult to, from the onset, devise a structure for an essay. Other than the introduction, body and conclusion sections I tend to not have predetermined subsections until I have written whatever comes to mind on the subject. Once I have written all these thoughts and run out of things to say on the subject I start to order them into a draft structure, following which I start to review and revise grammar and spelling. Once I have the initial draft I return to ensure the flow of the paper makes sense that each paragraph has a clear message and that one idea flows into the next. Finally, I include intext referencing for those arguments and ideas that require support or credit. (EUCLID 2015, 2-5).

In consideration of my usual writing process, the section on writing an essay contained in the section on pages 2-5 did provide some insight into improving my way of constructing an essay. I consider it complimentary to my process by providing some additional guidance on ensuring that my thoughts and ideas stay on track and communicating my message clearly and concisely.

4) DOCUMENT FORMAT

I was delighted to learn that a standard format in MS Word, with the use of styles, is employed for all papers (EUCLID 2015, 52). I find this practise very useful indeed as it eliminates concerns around formatting. I have employed the use of styles in my own paper writing (in line with the formatting requirements of the University of South Africa) and found it to be very effective to ensure uniformity and consistency (EUCLID 2015, 52). In addition, it simplified the use of other functions in MS Word such as the table of contents/figures/tables and saves much time. Although slightly different from my usual formatting styles, I do not foresee any issues with regards to the use of the templates.

5) CONCLUSION

I found the content of the assigned study material a valuable guide to spark a personal reflection on my existing writing skills, process and style. This reflection opened me up to some possibilities for improvement and this response paper explored just this. It was therefore not a discussion on the academic value and/or relevance on the contents of the study material, but rather a reflection on the application thereof. The assigned study material provided a welcome refresher of matters around proper academic writing such as grammatical errors, the differences between the UK and US conventions, referencing, writing and formatting styles. Although some of the information is new and will likely only become clear once implemented (particularly referencing), I am sure that it will assist in improving my writing skills. I look forward to applying some of the new concepts and applications and brushing up on my existing skills as I move forward in the programme.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA401 Coursepack: Period 1*.
<https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf>
(accessed June 2, 2019).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.